

GLUCOSE DEHYDROGENASE FROM GERMINATED SEEDS OF GREEN AND BLACK GRAMS (*PHASEOLUS RADIATUS* AND *PHASEOLUS MUNGO*, LINN.)

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An oxidising enzyme from germinating green gram (and black gram) is described. It acts on glucose both aerobically and anaerobically and is, therefore, a perfect dehydrogenase. Methylene blue cannot be used as a hydrogen acceptor. It inhibits the enzyme by about 25%. 2:6-Dichlorophenol-indophenol blue can act as an acceptor. Galactose and mannose are also oxidised by the same enzyme and the latter is, therefore, group-specific. Fructose, xylose, arabinose are not affected. Narcotics inhibit the dehydrogenase, while potassium cyanide and hydrogen sulphide inhibit the oxidase factor. Flavin, adrenaline and ascorbic acid cannot act as carriers but glutathione can, the acceleration being about 8%. The enzyme appears to contain an aldehyde group, like Harrison's glucose dehydrogenase from animal sources. The product of oxidation is probably gluconic acid. Physiological significance of the presence of the enzyme in plants is discussed.

In course of some experiments, it was noticed that an aqueous extract of germinated seedlings of green gram (*Phaseolous radiatus*) absorbs a large amount of oxygen, when shaken in a Warburg-Barcroft vessel. The phenomenon occurred without the apparent addition of any substrate. Heating of the solution to 60° for 5 minutes prior to placing it in the vessel stopped the process completely showing that the phenomenon was due to the presence of some oxidising enzyme. The fact that the process was being continued without the apparent addition of any substrate, might be due to the donator being already present in the extract. With this point in view, attempts have been made to characterise the enzyme in question. With this purpose the solution is first dialysed in parchment paper against large volumes of distilled water and then different substances are added to the dialysed extract and the oxygen uptake is noted. It is found that addition of glucose to the dialysed extract produces a marked increase in the absorption of oxygen showing that the enzyme in question acts on glucose. Preliminary phenylhydrazine tests for glucose in the original extract have also been performed and characteristic crystals of osazone are found under the microscope, thus giving an indirect support to the previous conclusion.

Enzymes acting on glucose have been detected in widely different sources. Quastel and Wooldridge (*Biochem. J.*, 1928, 22, 689) found this enzyme in *B. coli*. Muller (*Biochem. Z.*, 1929, 218, 211) detected this enzyme in *Aspergillus niger*. He believed it to be an oxidase, in as much as it did not accelerate the reduction of methylene blue nor was hydrogen peroxide formed in the process of glucose oxidation. Harrison (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, 26, 1016) was first to isolate glucose dehydrogenase from animal sources. The enzyme converted glucose into gluconic acid (*Biochem. J.*, 1932, 26, 1295). It could function both anaerobically (with methylene blue as hydrogen acceptor) and aerobically in oxygen with *cytochrome-C* as a carrier (Hawthorne and Harrison, *Biochem. J.*, 1939, 33, 1573). A co-enzyme was necessary for its activity as was first shown by Mann (*ibid.*, 1932, 26, 785) and later confirmed by Harrison (*ibid.*, 1933, 27, 383). Ogston and Green (*ibid.*, 1935, 29, 1983) studied the action of different carriers on the enzyme and showed that methylene blue, yellow pigment and glutathione could accelerate the reaction. Harrison (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, B, 113, 150) also studied the chemical nature of the enzyme and showed that the enzyme contained an aldehyde group.

Franke and Lorenz (*Annalen*, 1937, 532, 1) and Franke and Deffner (*ibid.*, 1939, 541, 117) studied Muller's oxidase and showed that it was not an oxidase, but a dehydrogenase in as much as it could use quinone, indophenol derivatives and *p*-phenylenediamine as hydrogen acceptors. It also oxidised glucose to gluconic acid.

Ogura (*Acta Phytochim.*, 1939, 11, 127) also detected a glucose dehydrogenase in *Aspergillus oryzae*. It differed from that of Muller and Franke in that it did not react directly with oxygen. Methylene blue could not serve as a hydrogen acceptor and in this respect it was identical with Muller's and Franke's enzyme but different from Harrison's. Mention should also be made of Yudkin's work (*Biochem. J.*, 1934, 28, 1463) on the enzyme of *B. coli* and of Tarr's work (*ibid.*, 1933, 27, 141) on the enzyme of the spores of vegetable tissues.

Thus, while there is so much study about the nature and action of the enzyme from animal and bacterial sources and from molds, no evidence has been presented, as yet, of its presence in higher plants. The discovery of the enzyme in germinating green gram is thus interesting, it being the first observation of its kind in higher plants and consequently a study of the properties and action of this enzyme has been made. It has been found that the enzyme is a dehydrogenase of "aerobic type", functioning both aerobically and anaerobically. Methylene blue cannot serve as a hydrogen acceptor in anaerobic oxidation but quinone and dichlorophenol derivatives can. Narcotics inhibit the enzyme very greatly while potassium cyanide and hydrogen sulphide inhibit the aerobic activity of the enzyme without affecting the dehydrogenating action. Like Harrison's enzyme, it can use glutathione as a carrier and seems to contain an aldehyde group. Unlike Harrison's enzyme its action is inhibited rather than accelerated by methylene blue and it requires no co-enzyme.

EXPERIMENTAL

Most of the experiments were carried out under aerobic conditions. The anaerobic method was adopted only in the case where the chemical nature of the enzyme was determined.

Aerobic experiments were done in Warburg—Barcroft apparatus. One Barcroft vessel contained the enzyme, buffer and water without substrate to find out the amount of oxygen absorbed in the blank. Some amount of oxygen absorption in the blank was always found even after continuing the dialysis of the aqueous extract long enough and it was always taken into account. The inner cup of all vessels contained 0.3 ml. *N*-NaOH and filter paper, according to the technique of Dixon and Elliott (*Biochem. J.*, 1930, 24, 820).

It must, however, be noted that the oxidising capacity of different enzyme preparations varied from preparation to preparation and as such no comparison between results with different preparations are possible. However, each series of experiments was carried out with one and the same enzyme solution and if possible, at the same time.

Anaerobic experiments were done in Thunberg tubes. In each experiment a series of tubes was used, each containing a total volume of 4.5 c.c. of the contents. Each tube contained 0.5 c.c. of 1/5000 dichlorophenol-indophenol blue, 0.5 c.c. of *M*/10 glucose solution and 1 c.c. of enzyme solution. The tubes were evacuated at room temperature with the help of a Cenco Hyvac pump. The time for complete reduction was observed. Blank experiments were also performed side by side. Both aerobic and anaerobic activity was measured at 38°

Preparation of the Enzyme.—Seeds of green gram were washed and then kept immersed in water for 24 hours, during which they swelled and the outer coats burst, the radicle of each seed appearing to come out of the micropyle. The water was then drained away and the seeds were spread on moist sand in a shady place for germination. When the plumule just began to come out—a process which needed about 3 days—the seeds were washed free from sand, finally washed with distilled water and ground well in a mortar with acid-washed sand.

About twice its volume of distilled water was then added and the whole allowed to stand about half an hour in a refrigerator, after which the extract was pressed out of muslin. The extract was taken in a conical flask and allowed to stand for another 45 minutes to 1 hour in the refrigerator, during which time a large amount of starch and proteins of the globulin type separated at the bottom. The clear extract from the top was syphoned out and dialysed in a parchment paper against large volumes of distilled water with frequent changes. For aerobic experiments, extracts usually dialysed for 3 days were found to be most convenient, whereas for anaerobic activity measurements, 2 days' dialysis sufficed.

Proceeding in exactly the same way a similar enzyme preparation was obtained from black gram (*Phaseolus mungo*, Linn.). Since in every case except the optimum p_n , the properties of the latter enzyme are very much akin to those of the enzyme in green gram, it was not studied in detail. Only the optimum p_n was determined in this case. The results are given below.

TABLE I
Determination of optimum p_n

	Green gram						Black gram					
p_n of the medium	5.9	6.2	6.5	6.8	7.1	7.4	5.6	5.9	6.2	6.5	7.1	7.4
Oxygen absorption in /nl per 30 minutes	70.6	126.7	193.8	120.7	76.0	54.8	132.0	183.9	125.8	69.4	65.6	69.0

In each of the Barcroft vessels were taken 2 c.c. of the enzyme solution, 1 c.c. of $M/10$ glucose and 4 c.c. of $M/6$ phosphate buffer and water making a total volume of 8 c.c. The final concentration of the buffer was nearly $M/10$.

A difficulty met with in the determination of optimum p_n was that the acidic oxidation product of the enzyme changed the p_n of the medium considerably towards the acid side. It was avoided by the use of phosphate buffer at a higher concentration. Preliminary trials showed that $M/6$ phosphate buffer added in 4 c.c. portions to every 7-8 c.c. of the total volume would maintain the p_n constant for at least 3 hours. Further, at this concentration it was not inhibitory to the enzyme system. Table II shows the effect of concentration of the substrate on the enzymic activity.

TABLE II

Contents of the cup : 2 c.c. enzyme, 1 c.c. substrate, 4 c.c. phosphate buffer and 1 c.c. water. p_n 6.5. Temperature = 38°

Molarity of the substrate	$N/40$	$M/60$	$M/80$	$M/100$	$M/200$	$M/400$
Oxygen absorption in /nl per two hours	950.4	944.2	824.1	654.1	446.7	359.7

The maximum rate reached when the concentration of the substrate was about 0.025 *M*. The half-speed concentration (*i.e.* the Michaelis constant K_m) is very nearly equal to 0.005 *M*, a value which like that of Harrison's enzyme (0.007 *M*) is an exceptionally high value for an oxidising enzyme.

Inactivation by Heat.—The enzyme solution (5 c.c.) was placed in each of several test-tubes kept immersed for 10 minutes in baths at different temperatures ranging from 35° to 52°. The solutions were cooled and the activity of each sample measured manometrically by taking 2 c.c. portions of the enzyme solutions in every 4 c.c. portion of *M/6* phosphate buffer and adding 1 c.c. of *M/10* glucose to each of them. Up to 40° the activity remained intact, after which there was gradual inactivation and at 52° the enzyme was completely inactivated. The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Temperature of the experiment = 38°

Temperature of incubation	35°	40°	42°	44°	48°	50°	52°
Oxygen absorption in /ul per hour	267.7	270.3	268.7	203.2	87.4	17.1	Nil

Temperature Coefficient.—It is known that within the temperature zone, where there is practically no temperature inactivation of the enzyme system, the ratio of velocities at two temperatures, differing by 10° from one another, is a characteristic constant varying slightly with different enzyme systems and is near about 2 to 3. Experiments of this kind, performed with the enzyme in question, revealed a value near about 2.5 to 2.6. The following are the results (Table IV).

TABLE IV

Temp. at which the activity is measured.	Activity (in /ul oxygen per hr.)	Q_{10}
25°	56.2	2.59
35°	145.8	
30°	92.0	2.51
40°	130.2	

TABLE V

Enzyme.	Substrate.	Temp.	Q_{10}
Xanthine oxidase	Hypoxanthine		2.0 ¹
Root peroxidase	Leucomalachite green.	5-15° 15-25°	2.0 ² 2.0
<i>B. Coll</i> succinoxidase	Succinate	30-40 40-50°	2.1 ³ 2.1
Glucose dehydrogenase of green gram	Glucose	25-35° 30-40°	2.6 ⁴ 2.5

It will perhaps be interesting to compare these values with those found with some other respiratory enzymes, as shown in the Table V.

Inhibitors

Action of Narcotics.—According to the classical work of Keilin (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928-29, B, 104, 251) the inhibitory action of narcotics on the activity of respiratory enzymes is

- 1 Dixon and Thurlow (*Biochem. J.*, 1924, 18, 976).
- 2 Willstätter and Weber (*Annalen*, 1926, 488, 175).
- 3 Quastel and Whetham (*Biochem. J.*, 1924, 18, 519).
- 4 Present investigation.

due to their action on the dehydrogenating part of the latter. The narcotics become absorbed on the enzyme surface and the reaction velocity is inhibited owing to the displacement of the reacting substance in question by them. If, therefore, the enzyme is left for sometime in contact with the narcotic before the addition of the substrate, the maximum inhibitory power is exerted. The following experiments were done to see the action of narcotics on the enzyme.

2 C.c. portions of the enzyme were taken in different Barcroft vessels with 3 c.c. portions of phosphate buffer (M/6). 1 C.c. of narcotic at suitable concentration was added to each and the cups were shaken for 20 minutes in the thermostat with the taps closed. At the end of this interval, 1 c.c. of substrate was added to each and the oxygen uptake was measured. The activity was compared with that of the control which was also treated in the same manner excepting exposure to the narcotic and the inhibition noted. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE VI

Temperature of the experiment = 35°. Duration of the experiment = 1 hr. 20 mins.

Inhibitor.	Final conc.	% inhibition.	Inhibitor.	Final conc.	% inhibition.
Vanillin	5%	45	Barbitone	5%	69
	1	63		1	39
	0.1	18		0.1	26
Urethane	5	88	Octyl alcohol	0.1	99
	1	52		0.02	82
	0.1	12			

Unfortunately the enzyme solutions employed in the experiments with different inhibitors were of different degrees of purity, and as such the results are not strictly comparable. One thing is, however, noticeable; octyl alcohol is highly inhibitory to the enzyme and with its suitable concentration the activity can be practically completely suppressed. The action of vanillin is also noticeable.

Action of Potassium Cyanide.—Cyanide at a concentration of 0.001M inhibits the enzyme by about 66%. On increasing the concentration, the inhibition also increases and a concentration of 0.01 M-potassium cyanide inhibits the enzyme activity by about 91%. In carrying out these experiments, alkali in the inner cup of the Barcroft vessel was replaced by an alkali-cyanide mixture of suitable concentration according to the direction of Krebs (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 1620). The results are summed up in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Potassium cyanide

M/6-phosphate buffer = 4 c.c. Enzyme soln. = 2 c.c. Glucose = 1 c.c. KCN or water (control expt.). Temp. = 38°.

Time in min.	0	15	30	45	60	75	90
Substances	Oxygen absorption in ml						
Glucose alone	0	20.1	39.2	60.2	91.4	123.5	174.7
Glucose and KCN (0.01 M)	0	4.1	6.3	11.5	12.0	13.8	15.0
Glucose and KCN (0.001 M)	0	15.2	30.7	41.7	47.6	51.2	59.5

TABLE VIII

Other inhibitors

1 C.c. inhibitor or water (control expt.). Duration of the expt. = 1 hour 30 min. Other conditions same as in Table VII.

Inhibitors.	O ₂ absorption in ml		
	In presence of inhibitor.	Control.	Inhibition.
Sodium pyrophosphate (M/50)	195.5	212.5	8.0%
M/250-Na ₂ S	70.8	"	66.7
M/10-NaF	175.3	"	17.5
CuSO ₄ (0.2 mg.)	95.6	"	55.0
Fe (0.2 mg.)	213.2	"	Nil

Other Inhibitors.—Sodium sulphide ($M/250$) produces a strong inhibition on the oxidase factor of the enzyme. Inhibition by NaF ($M/10$) and sodium pyrophosphate ($M/50$) is relatively small. The addition of 0.2 mg. of copper inhibited the enzyme by 55% while iron at similar concentrations both in the reduced and oxidised forms was without any effect (Table VIII).

Specificity

Specificity of the Donator.—The dehydrogenase of the green gram oxidises galactose and mannose in addition to glucose. Fructose is not very much oxidised, while xylose and arabinose are not oxidised at all. The action on galactose and mannose is appreciable in comparison with that on glucose, as the following table will show.

TABLE IX

Substrate	Glucose	Galactose	Mannose
Oxygen absorption in μ l per 2 hrs.	642.3	403.7	213.7

The glucose dehydrogenase of Harrison (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, 26, 1016) also has appreciable action on galactose and mannose. Franke and Deffner (*loc. cit.*) in working with Muller's oxidase have also stated that the rates of oxidation of glucose, mannose and galactose by the enzyme are in the ratio 1 : 0.07 : 0.14. The enzyme from *Aspergillus oryzae*, isolated by Ogura, similarly acts on mannose, galactose and xylose. Whether all these substances are oxidised by the same enzyme or by different enzymes in the same preparation, is not definitely known and no experiments in this line have been carried out. It seemed, therefore, of interest to study this phenomenon since it might yield information as to whether the enzyme is specific for glucose, or it is group-specific. With this object in view the following experiments were done.

If two substrates are oxidised by the same enzyme, it is to be expected that the rate of oxidation of the two substrates together in optimum concentration, will be less than the sum of the oxidation rates of each substrate alone. When glucose was added to the enzyme in optimum concentration, the further addition of galactose or mannose was not found to increase the rate of oxidation. Table X shows the results

TABLE X

Competition between glucose and galactose.				Competition between glucose and mannose.					
Glucose	0.025 M	0.025 M	0	0	Glucose	0.025 M	0.025 M	0	0
Galactose	0	0.025 M	0.025 M	0.05 M	Mannose	0	0.025 M	0.025 M	0.025 M
O ₂ uptake (μ l/30 mins.)	125.0	112.0	79.7	75.2	O ₂ uptake (μ l/30 mins.)	106.2	89.0	37.4	37.0

Preliminary trials showed that optimum concentrations of galactose and mannose were reached at 0.02 M and 0.017 M respectively. The above experiments thus clearly show that the same enzyme acts on glucose, galactose and mannose. The enzyme is, therefore, group-specific.

Specificity of the Acceptor.—As mentioned before, the enzyme catalyses the oxidation of glucose by molecular oxygen and by oxidation-reduction indicators such as 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol derivatives. Methylene blue is unable to act as an hydrogen acceptor. It inhibits the

enzyme action by about 25%. Appropriate experiments also showed that flavin, adrenaline and ascorbic acid were incapable of acting as intermediate carriers while glutathione could, the acceleration being about 8%.

TABLE XI

Effect of carriers on glucose dehydrogenase

Carrier.		/ul O ₂ per hr. absorption with		% acceleration.
Name	Conc.	control.	carrier.	
Flavin	107/c.c.	256.8	248.9	Nil
Adrenaline	(1 mg./8 c.c.)	225.5	230.4	„
		(with adrenaline alone = 10)		
Glutathione	(4 mg./8 c.c.)	238.1	257.7	8.2
Ascorbic acid	(5 mg./8 c.c.)	250.0	266.3	Nil
		(with ascorbic acid alone = 200.2)		
Methylene blue	(1/60,000)	211.2	157.9	25.2 (inhibition)

TABLE XII

Effect of xanthine oxidase on glucose dehydrogenase

Temp. of the expt. = 38°. Dye used = 0.5 c.c. of (1/5000)2: 6-dichlorophenol-indophenol

No. of tube.	Glucose dehydrogenase of green gram.	Glucose (M/10).	Xanthine oxidase.	Reduction time.
1	1 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	1 c.c.	> 3 hours
2	1	0.5 c.c.	„	18 mins
3	1	—	1 c.c.	> 3 hours
4	1	—	—	3 hours

Purification of the Enzyme

Precipitation with dilute acetic acid, acetone, alcohol and alcohol-ether mixtures was tried but all yielded inactive preparations. Precipitation by half or full saturation with ammonium sulphate in acid, alkaline and neutral regions was tried but with no success. The enzyme seemed to be adsorbed partly on kaolin but no satisfactory method of elution was found out. It should also be noted in this connection that seedlings (3 days old) yielded the most active preparation and after 5 days the activity was very low.

Absence of Co-enzyme.—The enzyme was not inactivated by dialysis. Further, the addition of boiled extract did not increase the activity. No co-enzyme is, therefore, necessary for this dehydrogenase.

Aldehyde group of the Enzyme.—Working with the glucose dehydrogenase of animal source Harrison (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, B., 113, 150) found it to contain an aldehyde group. The principle of his experiment was to see the action of xanthine oxidase and of sodium bisulphite on the enzyme. It is known that xanthine oxidase acts on aldehydes (as also on purines) and that sodium bisulphite in acid pH combines with aldehydes. If, therefore, the enzyme in question contained an aldehyde group, it should be inhibited by xanthine oxidase as well as by sodium bisulphite in acid pH. Experiments corroborated this fact. In order to show that the inhibition by xanthine oxidase was not due to mutual inactivation of the two enzymes, Harrison showed that his dehydrogenase did not inhibit the activity of xanthine oxidase at all. Further in a second series of experiments he showed that heating of the xanthine oxidase to progressively increasing temperatures, previous to incubation with glucose dehydrogenase, decreased its property of inhibiting the latter, thus showing definitely that the inhibition of glucose dehydrogenase was due to the activity of the xanthine oxidase.

As xanthine oxidase might act on the aldehyde or purine group, he confirmed his assumption by allowing sodium bisulphite in acid pH to act on his enzyme and found definite inhibition with the latter, thus establishing beyond doubt the presence of an aldehyde group in the enzyme.

Working in exactly the same way with the dehydrogenase of the green gram, it was found that xanthine oxidase definitely inhibited the enzyme. Xanthine oxidase was prepared according to the method of Dixon and Kodama (*Biochem. J.*, 1926, 20, 1104). The enzyme solution was prepared by dissolving a suitable amount of the powder in water, bringing to the required p_n (6.5) by cautious addition of dilute sodium hydroxide and centrifuging to obtain a perfectly clear solution. 1 C.c. of the enzyme solution could decolourise 0.5 c.c. of 1/5000-methylene blue in 5 minutes with 0.2 mg. of hypoxanthine as the substrate. The results are given in Tables XII and XIII. Because of the inability of the dehydrogenase of green gram to decolourise methylene blue, 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol blue was used in measuring its activity. The activity of xanthine oxidase was measured, as usual, with methylene blue as hydrogen acceptor.

The fact that in tube (4) the time of decolourisation of indophenol blue is less than that of (1) and (3) might be due to the fact that a small amount of glucose remained tenaciously in the extract and was not removed even after prolonged dialysis.

TABLE XIII

Effect of heated xanthine oxidase on glucose dehydrogenase of green gram

Temp. = 38°. Time of heating = 5 minutes

No. of tube.	Dehydrogenase.	Glucose M/10.	Xanthine oxidase.	Reduction time of indophenol.	time of methylene blue.	No. of tube.	Dehydrogenase.	Glucose M/10.	Xanthine oxidase.	Reduction time of indophenol.	time of methylene blue.
1	1 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	—	16 mins.	—	4	1 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	1 c.c. (heated to 65°)	>3 hrs.	9½ mins.
2	"	"	1 c.c. (unheated)	>3 hrs.	5 mins.	5	"	"	1 c.c. (heated to 70°)	25 mins.	31 mins.
3	"	"	1 c.c. (heated to 55°)	>3 hrs.	7½ mins.	6	"	"	1 c.c. (heated to 75°)	16½ mins.	—

From the results in Tables XII and XIII it is seen that xanthine oxidase appears to inhibit the activity of glucose dehydrogenase of the green gram. That the diminution of the activity of the latter is not due to the mutual action of the two enzymes was shown. Thus it was found that 1 c.c. of the above xanthine oxidase solution used, decolourised 0.5 c.c. of 1/5000 methylene blue in nearly 5 minutes in presence of 0.2 mg. of hypoxanthine and 1 c.c. of the glucose dehydrogenase in question. The latter enzyme, therefore, did not inhibit the former.

For confirmation of the presence of the aldehyde group in the enzyme the action of sodium bisulphite, as mentioned above, must be seen. But several difficulties arose. Thus when sodium bisulphite (in acid p_n) was added to a mixture containing glucose dehydrogenase of the green gram and 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol blue, the colour of the latter disappeared instantly, making anaerobic experiments impracticable. In aerobic experiments also there was a large oxygen uptake due to autoxidation of the bisulphite. Preliminary incubation of sodium bisulphite produced no result as was previously shown by Harrison (*loc. cit.*). However, it was found that some sort of competition took place between sodium bisulphite (in acid p_n only) and glucose for the enzyme surface in all aerobic experiments. This could not be the case if sodium bisulphite did not tend to combine with the aldehyde group of the enzyme.

Products of Oxidation

It was mentioned before that the product of oxidation of glucose is acidic, as was evinced by the change in the p_n of the solution when buffer of low concentration was used in the experiments. Harrison (*loc. cit.*) working with glucose dehydrogenase of animal tissues isolated gluconic acid as the oxidation product. The same substance was also found by Franke and Lorenz (*loc. cit.*) and by Ogura (*loc. cit.*) as the oxidation product of glucose by their respective enzymes. Attempts were, therefore, made to see whether the oxidation product of glucose by the action of the enzyme from green gram was identical with gluconic acid. No satisfactory quantitative method has as yet been developed. However, proceeding in a method similar to that of Harrison (*loc. cit.*) with slight modifications, some crystals of calcium gluconate were found in alcoholic medium. In broad outline the method involves precipitation of the protein with 80% alcohol, adding basic lead acetate to the concentrated filtrate to precipitate gluconic acid as lead salts, removing the lead by hydrogen sulphide, and addition of calcium carbonate to the acidified liquid. The calcium gluconate is then precipitated with alcohol and crystallised from 30% alcohol.

DISCUSSION

From the above results, it seems that the enzyme of green gram stands midway in properties between the dehydrogenase of Harrison and that of Muller, Franke and Ogura. Like Harrison's enzyme it is a perfect dehydrogenase, functioning both aerobically and anaerobically, using glutathione as a hydrogen acceptor and having the same aldehyde group in the enzyme molecule. The similarity is pushed still further by their high Michaelis constant. Unlike Harrison's enzyme it cannot use methylene blue as a hydrogen acceptor but can decolourise 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol blue with advantage. It does not require the presence of a co-enzyme and in these respects it is similar to the enzyme systems of the molds. Some properties are, however, common to all of them; thus all of them oxidise glucose to gluconic acid, can function both aerobically (except the enzyme of *aspergillus oryzae* of Ogura) and anaerobically. All are group-specific rather than strictly specific to glucose alone. The inability of all of them except Harrison's enzyme to decolourise methylene blue, points out that the oxidation-reduction potential of the latter enzyme is more negative than that of the former. Is it then due to the fact that all of them contain the same aldehyde group (active group?) but a different colloidal carrier or Träger?

The sensitivity of the oxidase factor to the action of potassium cyanide and hydrogen sulphide (and to a less extent to fluoride and pyrophosphate) points to the probability of cytochrome systems functioning in the aerobic process. But the fact that even at a concentration of 0.01M potassium cyanide the inhibition is not 100% also points to the presence of some additional cyanide-stable system or systems. Several carriers were tested and all were found to be inactive with the exception of glutathione but other carriers, such as pyrocyanine were not available and as such the problem cannot be said to be finally settled.

It has been shown by Hawthron and Harrison (*loc. cit.*) that in the aerobic oxidation of glucose glucose dehydrogenase from animal tissues can use cytochrome *a*, *b* or *c* as carriers, provided some other factor, diaphorase of Euler, is present. In the case of the enzyme from green gram, it is not known whether any one of *a*, *b* and *c* or all of them can function as carriers or whether the presence of diaphorase is necessary for reduction of cytochrome systems. And indeed it cannot be known unless some method of purifying the enzyme in question is found and herein we failed inspite of a good number of careful experiments with different reagents.

Physiological Significance

The isolation of glucose dehydrogenase in green and black grams raises a number of questions as regards its possible significance to them and to the plant systems at large. Are these plants dependent for their supply of energy upon the oxidation of glucose in their life-course or since the enzyme is found in germinated seeds, at least in the period of germination? In view of the fact that in aqueous extract of the enzyme there is always found some amount of glucose even in spite of prolonged dialysis with consequent oxygen uptake in the blank, the conclusion seems unavoidable. However, considering the wide diversity which plants display amongst themselves, such generalisation now is premature until a systematic and careful study is made of the distribution and mode of action of the enzyme in different plant systems or at least in some representative members.

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